

TABLE 2—ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF 7-(α -SUBSTITUTED SULPHONAMIDO)METHYL AND 7-(α -SUBSTITUTED SULPHONAMIDO)PHENYL-8-HYDROXYQUINOLINES

Organism	Zone of inhibition (mm) by								
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	S'
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	20	18	08	13	07	10	06	12	—
<i>Vibrio cholerae</i>	21	—	—	08	18	10	18	18	35
<i>Achromobacter hydrophilis</i>	—	18	12	—	—	16	17	06	35
<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	—	08	—	13	12	14	12	09	24
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	23	10	10	—	18	10	19	20	21
<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	22	—	16	14	—	—	20	24	22
<i>Plesiomonas shigellaides</i>	20	28	14	10	20	18	26	08	41
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	23	06	08	—	—	12	20	10	—
<i>Citrobacter</i>	14	20	10	12	16	10	28	18	36
<i>C. ovis</i>	30	24	12	—	15	09	10	—	40

S' = Sulphanilamide.

gellaiides, *Citrobacter* and *C. ovis*. Compounds A and G show a promising potency over the standard compound against *P. vulgaris*. Thus, the *in vitro* screening of the synthesized compounds against the organisms, although indicative of decreased potency, cannot be ruled out for quantitative screening. This decreased activity may be due to the lack of absorption under prevalent conditions.

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A Quick Method of Two Dimensional Thin Layer Chromatographic Separation of Human Serum Phospholipids and Their Identification

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ALL the 9-10 human serum phospholipids have been specifically extracted from 1 ml normal human serum by a particular organic solvent and resolved

and developed in two dimensional thin layer chromatogram. A specific solvent pair which gives straight solvent front (both ways), runs quickly, evaporates readily and possesses other favourable properties, has been used. Using the serum extract of normal healthy person, each of the nine phospholipids has been identified against known compounds and a 'standard map' of human serum phospholipids has been prepared. Total time required to study a pathological serum is only 4 hr.

Experimental

Selection of solvent pair :

The first requirement was the selection of a suitable solvent pair for two dimensional, thin layer chromatography. Considerable work has been done for the separation of phospholipids and getting all the 9-10 human serum phospholipids resolved and developed in the chromatogram. Nevertheless, many workers in the past have been confronted with the problem of selecting a suitable solvent pair for this purpose. Because of the polar nature of the compounds, a more polar solvent is required to move and develop them on silica gel layers. One of the widely used solvent mixtures that has been accepted by majority of workers is chloroform-methanol-water mixture of different proportions, such as (65 : 25 : 4)¹, (60 : 35 : 8)², etc. A number of solvent pairs have been tried but complete resolution and development of all the 9-10 phospholipids could not be achieved. It has been found in this laboratory after a long study, that if the universally accepted solvent system, chloroform-methanol-water is utilized in different proportions and the plate is coated with neutral silica gel the nine phospholipids could easily be resolved and developed. The first solvent used was chloroform-methanol-water mixture of 60 : 35 : 8 ratio and the second was a mixture of the same components in 65 : 25 : 4 ratio. Merits and demerits of this solvent pair have been discussed later.

Preparation of the plate :

20 × 20 cm glass plates were coated with silica gel G (Type 60, Art 7731, E. Merck) and used. For five plates, 40 g of the silica gel was taken in a glass

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stoppered flask and shaken with 77 ml triple distilled water for 1.5 min. The slurry was taken in the applicator adjusted with 0.020 cm slit and gently applied on the plates. The coated plates were air dried and preserved in a dust free covered box. Each plate, so prepared, was activated in a hot air oven at 90° for 0.5 hr. The plate was taken out and allowed to cool in room temperature and the sample was applied immediately with a microsyringe. Prior to the application of the sample, the starting point at one corner of the plate (1.5 cm away from either side) was marked. Two small scratches were made, with the help of a pin head at a distance of 12.7 cm from the bottom of the glass plate in either direction to observe and restrict the rise of the solvent front. Thus a 161.3 sq. cm 'field' was allowed in each plate for scattering of the phospholipids.

Extraction of phospholipids and preparation of sample :

0.5 ml clear serum of a normal healthy person, aged about 35, was poured into 7 ml isopropanol (A.R.) in each of two 15 ml centrifuge tubes, and the tubes closed with glass stopper. The mixture was shaken vigorously for exactly 30 sec. The tubes were centrifuged for 5 min at 1500 g and the upper isopropanol supernatant was decanted into a small beaker and reduced to ~0.3 ml. It has been found that this amount of isopropanol was adequate to completely deproteinize the serum and at the same time to completely extract all the phospholipids. The reduced solvent was further extracted with 0.5 ml chloroform (A.R.) and 50 μ l of the chloroform extract was applied on the starting point of the plate.

Running the plate in the solvent pair and development of phospholipid spots :

The 1st solvent was chloroform-methanol-water in the ratio 60 : 35 : 8. 103 ml of this solvent mixture was poured in a glass trough (10" \times 10" \times 5"). A piece of filter paper (8" \times 8") was dipped in the solvent at one side of the trough, and the trough was closed with a glass lid. The solvent was allowed to rise in the filter paper for ~0.5 hr till the inner atmosphere was saturated with the solvent vapour. The prepared plate with the sample applied at one corner was now dipped in the solvent and the solvent was allowed to run a distance of 12.7 cm. The plate was taken out and dried at 40° for 15 min. By this time the second solvent mixture in the ratio of 65 : 25 : 4 was ready. The dried plate was cooled, turned 90° clockwise and dipped in the 2nd solvent. Here also the solvent front was allowed to rise up to 12.7 cm. The phospholipids were thus distributed within an area of exactly 161.3 sq cm 'field'. The solvent was evaporated at room temp. for ~15 min.

The developed plate was sprayed with phosphomolybdic-perchloric acid reagent⁸, prepared by dissolving 0.5 g ammonium molybdate in 12 ml HCl-perchloric acid mixture (5 ml water + 5 ml 1 M HCl + 2 ml 70% perchloric acid). The sprayed

plates were heated at 85-90° for 15 min. 9-10 blue spots of phospholipids were thus obtained in a normal chromatogram.

Identification of individual compounds :

For reference purposes, all the phospholipids, excepting cardiolipin, lecithin, phosphatidyl inositol, phosphatidyl ethanolamine, were purchased from Sigma Chemical Co., USA and Koch Light laboratories, England. Cardiolipin and lecithin were available in this department in pure condition as these are routinely prepared from ox hearts and leg horn eggs, respectively for the preparation of VDRL antigen. Phosphatidyl ethanolamine was prepared from one hen's egg as per the procedure of Smith⁴. Phosphatidyl inositol was extracted in pure condition from ox brain in this laboratory as per Folch^{5,6}. While identifying each of the nine phospholipids, separate plates were run in two dimensions in the above solvent pair using a pair of known phospholipids, for example cardiolipin along with lecithin. As lecithin in serum has the highest concentration in comparison to other phospholipids [total phospholipids 256 mg (mean)/100 ml⁷ of which lecithin is ~125 mg (mean)/100 ml⁷]. Naturally, in all the test chromatograms lecithin spot is a very big one. Therefore, along with known lecithin whose position is known the position of other known phospholipids can thus be determined. In this way the position of each phospholipid could be identified and thus a 'standard map' of all the 9 phospholipids could be prepared. The phospholipids in serial number as given in the 'standard map' are :

1. Phosphatidic acid
2. Cardiolipin
3. Phosphatidyl ethanolamine
4. Phosphatidyl glycerol
5. Phosphatidyl choline (lecithin)
6. Phosphatidyl serine
7. Sphingomyelin
8. Phosphatidyl inositol
9. Lysolecithin

Results and Discussion

From the results of the study, it can be claimed that this is a quick method for separation of human phospholipids by two dimensional thin layer chromatography as it takes exactly 4 hr only, starting from extraction of the serum up to taking out the coloured chromatogram from the hot air oven, provided only that the silica gel-coated glass plates are readily available. However to produce the "standard map" two dimensional chromatography has to be done at least 10 times, each time taking lecithin as the reference compound. For example Fig. 1 shows the position of cardiolipin. In an identical way the positions of phosphatidyl ethanolamine and P-serine could be ascertained (Fig. 2). Fig. 3 is the 'standard map' showing the position of the nine usual serum phospholipids.

As regards the merits of the solvent pair used, the following are worth mentioning :

- (i) The components of the solvent mixture used being volatile, the solvent pair gives a straight solvent front both ways.
- (ii) Solvent runs quickly ; the solvent front reaches the 12.7 cm mark within 30-40 min.
- (iii) The components of the solvent being highly volatile, it takes only 5-10 min for complete evaporation. It must be mentioned here that in the 1st solvent where the ratio of water is a little more, a mild heating between 40-45° is necessary, otherwise blurring of the coloured spots takes place.

Fig. 1. Showing cardiolipin with reference to lecithin.

Fig. 2. Showing phosphatidyl ethanolamine with reference to lecithin

Fig. 3. Showing normal chromatogram of nine human serum phospholipids—(1) Phosphatidic acid, (2) Cardiolipin, (3) Phosphatidyl ethanol amine, (4) P-Glycerol, (5) P-Choline (lecithin), (6) P-Serine, (7) Sphingomyelin, (8) P-Inositol, (9) Lysolecithin. The big black spot at the top corner is cholesterol which could not be removed.

- (iv) The components of the solvent being polar organic covalent compounds, there is no scope of chemical reaction with the phospholipids in question.

It should, however, be admitted that complete resolution between sphingomyelin and phosphatidyl inositol could not be achieved. The two are clearly perceptible in some plates while not so in other plates.

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